

Electrical Material Properties From a Free-Space Time-Domain RF Absorber Reflectivity Measurement System

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Abstract: The scattering information obtained from the measurements of selected test structures is used to extract the relative permittivities of the various dielectric layers. Tests have been successfully conducted on single and multiple-layer dielectric panels, from which good estimates of material properties have been obtained. Results have been obtained in tests performed at both normal and oblique incidence. In addition, an edge-effect removal algorithm that significantly improves the estimated dielectric constant for small panels has recently been developed.

Introduction

There is currently much interest in characterizing the electrical properties of new composite materials that are being extensively used in aircraft and space vehicles. The electrical material properties have to be known if we are going to predict the electrical behavior of such structures. For instance, we might want to characterize the shielding performance of an aircraft structure made of a composite material in order to ensure proper protection of avionics systems from internal or external EMI. Unfortunately, many of these composite materials cannot be readily placed in conventional cavity, coaxial, waveguide, or stripline measurement fixtures [1,2]. In many cases, it is not possible to obtain a sample at all, since the material of interest might be located on an aircraft or space vehicle. Thus, we must pursue an alternative measurement strategy that circumvents these difficulties. One way to ameliorate this problem is to use a nondestructive materials measurement system that does not require the extraction of a core sample from the material under test. An approach that fulfills this requirement is a time-domain, free-space, bistatic scattering measurement system that has been developed by NIST [3]. In order to characterize the low-frequency, bistatic characteristics of the installed absorber system in the NIST anechoic chamber. There are two ways that this system can be deployed to test a given sample. (1) A sample rectangular panel of the material under test can be placed in the measurement system. (2) If a sample panel is not available, the measurement system can be deployed close to the desired material and in-situ tests are performed (for instance, one might want to evaluate a selected structural member of an aircraft.). Our free-space, time-domain measurement system, therefore, circumvents the difficulties that are inherent in evaluating composite materials in conventional materials measurement systems.

The scattering information obtained from the time-domain, free-space measurements is used to extract the desired electrical material properties from the panel or section under test. The method used for the extraction of the material properties is a slight modification of an approach developed by Randa [4]. The method consists of using an optimization procedure to fit measured scattering results in a least-squares sense to a plane-wave model. The electrical parameters of interest in the plane-wave model are adjusted until the mean-squared error between the model and the measured data is minimized. The values of the model parameters that result in a minimum error are the estimates of the desired electrical material properties.

Figure 1. Bistatic time-domain reflectivity measurement system.

The measurement system used to perform the material evaluation is depicted in fig. 1. The system is a direct-pulse time domain system consisting of a pulse generator, a 20 GHz digitizing sampling oscilloscope, a personal computer, two high-fidelity TEM horn antennas, and interconnecting cables for signal transmission and triggering. The pulse generator transmits a 10 V, 40 ps rise time step at a repetition rate of 50 kHz into the transmit TEM horn antenna which has a linear phase response and flat amplitude (± 2 dB) in the 100 MHz-5GHz frequency range. Due to the differentiating properties of TEM horn antennas in the

transmitting mode [5], the transmitted pulse rapidly becomes a short duration (250 ps) impulse with high (spatial) resolution capabilities. The transmitted impulse is reflected off the test sample back to the receive TEM horn antenna. The angle of incidence, along with the transmitted and received polarizations, are selected by adjusting the antenna positions and orientations. The received impulsive signal is detected and digitized by the 20 GHz sampling oscilloscope. The oscilloscope, therefore, functions as an ultra-wideband, high-fidelity receiver that accurately reconstructs the received impulsive waveform. The high noise inherent in broadband signal reception is overcome by employing waveform averaging - a process that is often used with a repetitive pulse generator. The digitized signal is then transferred to a personal computer for signal processing.

Obtaining the Scattering Characteristics

The received signal is dominated by strong environmental clutter (room reflections, etc.) and the large coupling that results from the close proximity of the transmitting and receiving antennas. This contamination must be greatly reduced in order to obtain useful information. The process of removing the undesired signal components is outlined in [6] and is summarized in the following steps:

- (1) The dielectric panel under test is placed in the measurement system. The resulting waveform is captured and stored.
- (2) The sample is then removed, and a background waveform is acquired.
- (3) The waveforms of steps 1 and 2 are subtracted. This step effectively removes the antenna-to-antenna coupling and most of the environmental clutter.
- (4) The waveform that is obtained in step 3 consists of the sample response and a signal component that emanates from the sample shadow region.
- (5) The shadow region waveform component of step 4 is deleted by time gating. This step removes the last environmental effects.
- (6) Steps 1-5 are repeated for a metal reference plate. This sequence is required to remove multiplicative system effects.

The final desired frequency-domain characteristics are found by Fourier transforming the time-gated waveforms of steps 5 and 6, and then taking the ratio of the resulting spectral amplitudes. This ratio is known as the backscatter coefficient and is given by

$$BC = \frac{|FT\{gated\ material\ wfm\}|}{|FT\{gated\ reference\ wfm\}|}, \quad (1)$$

where BC is the backscatter coefficient and FT denotes the Fourier transform. BC is a real quantity that is a function of frequency, the angle of incidence, and the selected polarization. Although phase information could be used to define a more general backscatter coefficient, it is not used in this process due to added complexities that must be introduced to the measurement procedures. The backscatter coefficient is a ratio of two scattered quantities, and it is a figure of merit for the amount of scattering from the material sample under test with respect to a metal reference plate. The ratio of eq. (1) is often called deconvolution [7].

Extraction of the Relative Permittivity

The backscatter coefficient data provide a basis for estimating the electrical permittivity properties of the sample under test. There are many approaches that we could take, with varying degrees of rigor. The approach used here involves several assumptions: (1) the dielectric panel under test exhibits very low dispersion - the dielectric constants of the various layers are essentially invariant with frequency (2) the losses of the various dielectric layers are negligible (3) close-proximity such as wave front curvature effects can be ignored (4) the backscatter coefficient results obey a one-dimensional plane-wave reflection coefficient model. These assumptions have been invoked to simplify the extraction process and to prove the concept of the measurement procedure. The methodology used here is flexible, so any or all of these assumptions can be eliminated - with the penalty of increased computational and analytical complexity.

In order to determine the dielectric constants of the materials under test, a one-dimensional plane-wave reflection coefficient model is compared with the measured backscatter coefficient data. If $|\Gamma(f_i)|$ denotes the plane-wave reflection computed from a 1-d modeling procedure [8], and $BC(f_i)$ is the measured backscatter coefficient data, the mean-squared error between the model and the measured data is

$$\delta = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (BC(f_i) - |\Gamma(f_i)|)^2, \quad (2)$$

where I denotes a particular frequency and N is the total number of frequencies. The desired dielectric constant is found by varying the dielectric constant in the plane-wave model until δ is minimized. This procedure has been implemented by using a pattern search optimization program [9,10] in conjunction with eq. (2). The optimization program adjusts the dielectric constant(s) in the plane-wave model in an iterative fashion until the error is minimized. The thicknesses of the dielectric panel being evaluated must be measured first and entered into the model before the optimization is undertaken. A plane-wave model is ideally suited for this scheme since the required reflection coefficient magnitudes can be computed rapidly at each step of the iteration, resulting in rapid convergence. A more exact numerical or analytical model could be used in this process, but the resulting computational effort would be increased.

Measurement Results

The first sample that was tested with the system was a Styrofoam panel with the dimensions of 2.0 x 2.0 x 0.51 m. The measurements were performed with the sample and reference plate, placed at a distance of 1.0 m from the TEM horn antenna apertures. Styrofoam, due to its low reflectivity, was first selected in order to assess the dynamic range of the measurement system. In addition, published permittivity data for this material [11,12] indicate that the previously listed assumptions are valid for this material.

Figure 2. Time-gated metal plate reference waveform.

The gated time-domain metal reference plate waveform is shown in fig. 2. The differentiating properties of the transmit horn are readily apparent - the applied fast rise time step function is transformed into a high-resolution impulsive waveform with a 250 ps duration, followed by a 2.5 ns negative step. The negative step is caused by induced charge on the outside of the antenna. The physical causes for this part of the waveform are described in detail in [13]. The gated time-domain Styrofoam waveform is shown in fig. 3.

Figure 3. Time-gated styrofoam waveform.

The waveform consists of an initial positive impulse, followed 300 ps later by a negative impulse of equal amplitude. These impulses correspond to the front and back surface reflections. The 300 ps delay in the peaks is consistent with the round-trip delay through the material (with the assumption of a relative dielectric constant close to 1). The deconvolved results, computed from eq. (1), are shown in fig. 4. The fact that Styrofoam has a dielectric constant that is close to that of air is apparent from the fact that the maximum backscatter coefficient is less than -30 dB. The corresponding optimized plane-wave model results using eq. (2) are also shown. The minimum mean-square error occurs at $\epsilon_r = 1.04$. This value was confirmed using a parallel-plate capacitance measurement and is consistent with a result quoted in Knott [12]. The frequency at which minimum reflection occurs is somewhat

lower than the plane-wave model predictions. A numerical study conducted at NIST using a finite-difference time-domain simulation [14] of the measurement system indicates that this offset is a direct result of performing measurements in close to the sample under test.

Figure 4. Measured and computed backscatter coefficient data for a 2m x 2m x 0.051 m Styrofoam sample at normal incidence $\theta=0^\circ$.

A three-layer dielectric panel, depicted in fig. 5 was also measured using this measurement system. The panel has length and width dimensions of 2 x 2 m, and it consists of a 0.051 m thick Nomex honeycomb layer, sandwiched by two thin (1 mm) layers of epoxy fiberglass, which give the panel high mechanical rigidity. The overall dimensions of this structure are nearly identical to those of the Styrofoam structure. This type of structure is commonly used on aircraft and space vehicles. The gated time-domain waveform at normal incidence is shown in fig. 6. The time-domain signature has completely different characteristics from that of the Styrofoam panel. Instead of two successive impulses, the signature is dominated by two doublets that occur at the front and back surface locations of the honeycomb layer. This result was somewhat puzzling since it was anticipated that the combination of very thin dielectric layers and a low dielectric constant honeycomb layer would result in a response very similar to that of the Styrofoam panel. After a thorough numerical and experimental investigation, we determined that the doublets were caused by a combination of front and back surface reflections from the two epoxy-fiberglass layers. Thus, the fiberglass layers reflect a differentiated version of the incident time-domain waveform, even though the layers are very thin a very surprising result. This has a very profound effect on the frequency-domain, backscatter coefficient results of fig. 7, where the frequency at which no reflection is approximately half of that of the Styrofoam panel. The thin dielectric layers completely alter the scattering characteristics of the structure. The frequency-domain results were optimized to a three-layer plane-wave model in which the fiberglass layers were assumed to have identical dielectric constants. This yielded estimates of $\epsilon_r = 1.07$ for the honeycomb layer and $\epsilon_r = 3.8$ for the epoxy fiberglass. Although this result as yet has not been checked using other measurement procedures (this would require destructive testing of the sample), the values appear to be approximately constant.

Figure 5. Side view of the 2m x 2m x 0.051 m honeycomb sample.

As an interim check of these results, backscatter measurements were performed on the honeycomb sample at various angles of incidence (see fig. 1). Results were obtained for two polarizations: (1) E-field parallel to the slab surface (2) H-field parallel to the slab surface. The measured oblique scattering results were then compared to a plane-wave oblique incidence model. The material properties used in the plane-wave model comparison were obtained from the normal incidence backscatter measurements. The measured and plane wave model results for $\theta=39^\circ$ are shown in fig. 8. The agreement between the measured and plane-wave model results is good for both polarizations. The scattering with the E-field parallel to the slab surface is considerably stronger than that of the other polarization. Also, the frequencies at which no reflection occurs for both measured and predicted results is different for each polarization. This split is due to having more than one dielectric layer.

Figure 6. Time-gated waveform obtained from the honeycomb sample.

Figure 7. Backscatter coefficient results for the honeycomb panel at normal incidence.

Figure 8. Measured and computed oblique incidence ($\theta=39^\circ$) honeycomb backscatter coefficients for two polarizations.

Edge-Effect Removal for a Polyethylene Slabs

Another series of backscatter measurements was performed on a 0.9 m x 0.9 m x 0.025 m polyethylene slab. This smaller slab size was selected to keep the weight down, as well as to make it easy to move it in and out of the measurement system. Unfortunately, this size makes it impossible to time-gate out the significant edge effects that are present in the scattered data. The edges strongly influence the results obtained, so a procedure has been developed to ameliorate this problem. Edge effects were not detectable in the Styrofoam or honeycomb structures.

The distance from the antennas to the sample was varied from 0.5 m to 1.25 m in 25 cm steps. The time-gated waveforms obtained are shown in fig. 9. The first large doublet in the received signal corresponds to a front-surface reflection followed by a reflection from the back surface of the slab. An examination of the 0.5 m waveform reveals a smaller secondary doublet following the initial front-surface/back-surface event. As the distance to the slab under test increases, the secondary doublet moves closer to the major

doublet, which indicates that it is caused by sample edge diffraction effects. In fact, as the measurement distance is increased to 1.25 m, the secondary doublet merges with the primary waveform. As

Figure 9. Time-domain normal incidence waveforms obtained as a function of distance.

the measurement distance to the polyethylene slab is increased, the amplitude of the major doublet decreases with increasing distance, and the shape and amplitude of the edge diffraction doublet is invariant with increasing distance. This characteristic can be exploited to reduce significantly the edge effects. As will be seen, the edge diffraction term can strongly influence the estimated dielectric constant, so a reduction of the edge effects improves the accuracy of the measurement system.

Figure 10. Waveforms obtained by sliding and subtracting to cancel edge effects. Waveforms obtained at 1.0 & 1.2 m are used.

Reducing the edge effect is straightforward. This process involves using time-domain waveforms from two different measurement distances. In the first step, the waveforms are shifted so that the timing of the edge-diffraction doublet are the same for both waveforms. The waveforms are then subtracted, which virtually removes the edge effects (due to the edge doublet shape and amplitude invariance). A result of this subtraction process is depicted in fig. 10, where the waveform obtained at a 1.2 m is subtracted from a corresponding 1.0 m result. The subtraction

sharpens up the waveform, and the removal of the edge component is readily observed. The resulting waveform consists of two major front-surface/back-surface doublets that are time shifted with respect to each other. If $f(t)$ denotes one of these major doublets, the subtracted waveform has the form

$$s(t) = f(t) + a f(t - \Delta) \quad (3)$$

, where Δ is the time delay between the two doublets and a is the amplitude scaling factor that is computed by taking the ratio of the peak amplitudes of the initial front (negative) surface reflection pulses. The delay is computed by taking the difference in the round-trip distances from the antenna aperture center to the sample edges and center respectively, and dividing the result by the speed of light. The final step of this procedure is carried out by performing a simple division in the frequency domain as follows:

$$|F(\omega)| = \frac{|S(\omega)|}{|[1 - \exp(-j\omega\Delta)]|} \quad (4)$$

, where ω is the radian frequency, $|S(\omega)|$ is the amplitude spectrum of eq. 3, and $|F(\omega)|$ is the final desired amplitude spectrum, with the sample edge effects removed. Figure 11 demonstrates the impact of this procedure on the amplitude spectrum obtained from the polyethylene slab measurements at 1.0 m and 1.2 m. The broad band diffraction amplitude ripples are no longer present after the edge effects have been removed.

The edge effects have a major impact on the estimated dielectric constants. When eq. (2) is applied over the frequency range of 500 MHz to 1 GHz with the edge diffraction included, the estimated relative dielectric constant is $\epsilon_r = 3.1$. When the edge effects are removed, $\epsilon_r = 2.4$ is obtained, which is much closer to $\epsilon_r = 2.25$ obtained by Von Hippel [11]. Similar results are also obtained by performing optimizations over different bandwidths. Clearly, the removal of edge effects greatly improves the accuracy of the estimated results.

Figure 11. Impact of edge effect removal on the amplitude spectrum of the backscattered signal.

Conclusions

Our time-domain free-space system for measuring absorber reflectivity can obtain scattering information from which electrical material properties can be extracted. This has been demonstrated on several different low-loss, low-dispersion dielectric panel structures where good results have been obtained using a straightforward approach. While the optimization procedure here is somewhat simplistic at this point, the concept of using a time-domain free-space measurement system to extract electrical material properties is clearly viable. The procedure is flexible, and it will be modified to improve the measurement accuracy for low-loss dielectric materials, as well as to accommodate more complex lossy, dispersive, and anisotropic materials. The development of an innovative edge-effect reduction procedure permits the accurate extraction of material properties from small sample panels for which the edge waveform component cannot be directly time gated. Research is currently being conducted at NIST to extend this reduction procedure to lossy and dispersive materials. This system is currently being evaluated, and a detailed uncertainty analysis of the measurement errors will be conducted in the near future.

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